

Progreso ti Umili: Public-Private Partnership Readiness of a Municipality in Nueva Vizcaya

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Abstract

The unanticipated collaboration between the traditionally opposing sectors of society—public and private—engendered the prominence of the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) as a strategic mechanism to address infrastructure and service delivery needs. In light of the technical complexity of the matter, a readiness assessment is imperative to evaluate the current state of venturing bodies and to identify gaps that need to be proactively resolved. In Nueva Vizcaya, the Local Government Unit of Solano (LGU) expressed interest in implementing PPP. This study assessed the readiness of municipal officials in the LGU through a mixed-methods approach, quantitative-qualitative, particularly descriptive-comparative analysis techniques and thematic analysis, on the basis of the legal framework and process of PPP. It also explored the perceived benefits and risks associated with PPP. The findings indicate that municipal officials are generally ready to implement PPP, possessing a moderate level of understanding and capability. Additionally, perceived benefits were mainly economic, while risks were attributed to governance administration and broader public sentiment. This study presents insights to municipal officials, experts, and stakeholders to collectively reinforce identified strengths and complete gaps to ensure ultimate readiness in the event of PPP implementation.

Keywords: *Fiscal, public administration, infrastructure, Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT), Local Government Unit (LGU), public services*

Introduction

Local Government Units (LGUs), in the conduct of their mandate, face challenges in the fiscal landscape that limit their provision of public services, and congruently, economic progress. Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, a rising municipality in the Philippines, is subject to the same problem as it grapples its way out of old infrastructures, inefficient water and energy supply, and limited healthcare, a few of the many public sector concerns. As a result, this instigates the interest in Public-Private Partnership (PPP).

With the advent of PPP, it has been recognized as a stimulant for economic growth and development. Since then, it has been a fiscal source for the Philippines at the national level and its local branches (The World Bank, 2019). In Asia, the Philippines is the first to institutionalize private sector involvement (Asian Development Bank, 2020). In 2023, RA 11966, commonly known as the "Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Code of the Philippines," was ratified. As of May 2025, the Philippines implemented 229 PPP projects, 136 in the national level and 93 in the local, and has 184 forthcoming. Nevertheless, the application of PPPs in smaller municipal settings has attracted less consideration than bigger projects implemented at the national scale (The World Bank, 2019).

LGU Solano, months before the enactment of the country's PPP Law, announced its plan to legislate its PPP Code and had undergone a briefing by the PPP Center. In its actualization, however, a successful PPP program calls for the readiness of its practitioners, particularly in the areas of the legal framework, implementation process, and perceived benefits and risks. This study, therefore, aims to assess the readiness of LGU Solano officials to implement PPPs and subsequently, produce a policy brief to reinforce strengths and address areas of improvement. It facilitates the responsible management of public funds and utilities for the improvement of the broader Solanoan community.

Ultimately, this study will contribute to the area of public administration, particularly in the local landscape, towards the broader progress of the country.

Methodology

The quantitative-qualitative study used a descriptive-comparative approach which assessed the readiness of selected LGU officials in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya in executing PPPs. The descriptive part of study emphasized the present condition of readiness of the Solano LGU officials, specifically on their understanding, perception, and capability regarding the subject. Whereas, the comparative approach assessed whether the respondents' positions, years of service, and attended seminars connected to PPPs have a significant difference with their understanding of the matter's legal framework.

The Municipality of Solano, a first-class municipality in Nueva Vizcaya, was the locale of the study. Solano was the ideal municipality for determining various components of their understanding, capabilities, and perspectives, which will be collected from the study's firsthand observations.

The participants of this study were selected through purposive sampling as certain criteria, particularly 34 respondents with governmental positions concerned in the implementation of PPP and affected representations were chosen. They served as the essential resources to make this study successful. The respondents are selected based on the composition of PPP Units of Local Implementing Agencies specified on the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of PPP Code of the Philippines.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Local government senior officials, technical personnel, finance personnel, and legal personnel responsible for the implementation of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya
2. Government departments involved in the planning, approval, and implementation of PPP projects in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.
3. Sectoral representatives that advocate for the interests, concerns, and needs of sectors affected by the implementation of PPP in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

Exclusion Criteria

1. LGU officials who do not hold positions or are not responsible for planning, approval, and implementation of PPP projects within Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.
2. Government departments who are not involved in the planning, approval, and implementation of PPP projects in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.
3. Sectoral representatives who are not concerned in the implementation of PPP in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

Research Instrument

This study used a researcher-made questionnaire with four parts. The first gathered demographic data on participants' positions, years in service, and PPP-related seminars attended. The second assessed their understanding of the PPP legal framework using a four-point Likert scale. The third measured their practical capabilities in the four stages of the PPP process—development, approval, competition, and cooperation—also using a Likert scale. Lastly, an open-ended section captured respondents' views on the benefits and risks of PPP implementation, offering insights for policy improvement.

Results and Discussion

Section 1. Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code

This section examines how well respondents understand the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of the PPP Code. Understanding the IRR is particularly important at the local government level, where decentralization places a significant portion of project execution responsibilities. By focusing on key areas—like knowledge of relevant laws, the roles of different stakeholders, and regulatory requirements—this section helps highlight both what local officials already know and where the gaps might be. The insights here can help shape better policy implementation and guide training efforts that meet the needs of people in the field.

Table 4

Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
I understand the laws governing PPP projects.	3.02	.71	Agree
I am aware of other laws and regulations related to PPP in the Philippines.	2.85	.65	Agree
I understand that the IRR gives the municipality the power to plan and carry out PPP projects.	3.11	.64	Agree
I know the roles of key agencies and actors in implementing PPP projects.	2.94	.73	Agree
I know the local government's responsibilities for infrastructure and service delivery in PPP projects.	3.26	.66	Agree
I am familiar with the regulatory framework, including rules for different PPP types and private-sector participation.	2.88	.76	Agree
I understand which projects are PPP and which ones are not.	2.94	.69	Agree
I know the requirements or approval that the municipality needs before making a deal on PPP projects.	2.85	.70	Agree
I understand that there are sectors where service delivery is a shared responsibility, as outlined in the PPP Code.	3.08	.62	Agree
I understand the process of PPP projects in local level.	2.91	.75	Agree
Overall Mean	2.98	.57	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Strong Disagree; 1.50 – 2.49: Disagree; 2.50 – 3.49: Agree; 3.50 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that the overall mean score is 2.98 with an SD of 0.57, which falls within the qualitative range of "Agree" (2.50 – 3.49). This indicates a moderate to high level of understanding among respondents of the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Public-Private Partnership (PPP).

Among the indicators, the highest mean score ($\bar{x}=3.26$) was understanding local government infrastructure and service delivery responsibilities under PPPs. This suggests greater awareness at the local governance level. Conversely, the lowest mean score ($\bar{x}=2.85$) was in awareness of other laws and regulations related to PPP and municipal approval requirements, highlighting these as areas of relatively weaker understanding. Despite being the lowest, these scores still fall under the “Agree” category. The relatively narrow range of standard deviations (0.62 to 0.76) indicates consistency in responses across all indicators.

The data suggests that respondents generally understand the basic framework of PPP-IRR, particularly in areas directly related to local implementation. This is not surprising, as local officials are often on the front lines of PPP execution, especially in the Philippines, where decentralization plays a significant role in public service delivery. However, the lower scores in legal and procedural technicalities (such as laws beyond the IRR and specific municipal requirements) indicate gaps in comprehensive legal knowledge. These could hinder efficient and compliant PPP project execution and may increase the risk of procedural errors or substandard agreements. These findings highlight the necessity for capacity-building initiatives by the LGU and the PPP Center that focus on enhancing legal knowledge and procedural standards among stakeholders engaged in PPPs, particularly within LGUs.

The current findings were aligned with other studies emphasizing the uneven understanding of PPP frameworks, particularly among subnational actors in the Philippines. Navarro (2024), in a policy paper from the Philippine Institute for Development Studies, noted that while legislative progress has been made through the newly enacted PPP Code, local LGUs struggle with PPPs' complex legal and procedural requirements. This reinforces the observed lower mean scores concerning regulatory comprehension and approval procedures. Similarly, Haydarov and Soriano (2016), in their report for the Asian Development Bank, documented that many LGUs lack the technical capacity and legal knowledge to initiate and implement PPP projects effectively. Their findings correspond to the lower mean scores in understanding other laws and procedural requirements, suggesting that LGU officials may not fully utilize the potential of PPP mechanisms without institutional support and training.

Section 2. Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code and Some Profile Variables

This section examines the varied levels of understanding among respondents regarding the IRR of the PPP Code and how these differences relate to certain profile variables, particularly position, years of service, and seminars attended related to PPP in the last 12 months. Through this, the factors that affect the readiness of PPP implementation in the chosen locale can be brought into light. Therefore, the significant gaps and areas for improvement in the planned venture of the LGU will be underlined, cascading into better policy formulation and implementation in the future.

Section 2.1. Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Position

This section presents a comparison of respondents' levels of understanding of the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of position. Respondents were categorized as officials belonging to the Executive Department and Legislative Department, as well as External Actors of the LGU Solano.

Table 5

Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Position

Mean Rating	Position	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	P-Value	Decision
Level of Understanding	Executive	2.66	.37	Agree	10.393	.006**	Reject Ho
	Legislative	3.45	.51	Agree			
	External	2.98	.28	Agree			
	Actors						
Overall		2.98	.57	Agree			

Significant Level at <0.05.

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Strongly Disagree; 1.50 – 2.49: Disagree; 2.50 – 3.49: Agree 3.50 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 5 displays that p-value of 0.006, implying a significant difference in the level of understanding of selected Solano LGU officials on the IRR of the PPP code in terms of position. Ultimately, respondents' answers across the three (3) categories resulted in "Agree" (\bar{x} =2.98, SD=0.57). In particular, the Executive had the lowest rating (\bar{x} =2.66, SD=0.37), while the Legislative generated the highest result (\bar{x} =3.45, SD=0.51). As such, while all positional categories have moderate understanding of the subject, level variations coincide with each of their officially mandated responsibilities.

The Legislative has the highest level of understanding compared to the two (2) categories, which originate from their mandate of policy formulation in the LGU. The enactment of the An Ordinance Enacting the Solano Investment and Incentives Code of 2023 and its own PPP Code in the pipeline are concrete examples of this instance. In addition, data reveals that the Legislative have attended the most number of seminars related to PPP during the last 12 months among the categories. Meanwhile, the Executive position, which is placed at the last rank, is in sharp contrast to that of the legislative branch, much so with their expected converging mandates. It is the implementing organ of the government; therefore, having a relatively low understanding of the subject can jeopardize the operations involving PPP and can deviate from the intended aim of the legislature.

This contradicts Habibon's (2021) synthesis, which suggests that the administrative capacity of the LGUs to execute infrastructure development projects in the Zamboanga Peninsula is notably high, as evidenced by the numerous projects realized through the political will of the Local Chief Executives (LCEs). Leaders recognize the essential procedures for implementation; yet, ingrained attitudinal and sociocultural behaviors within the system hinder its comprehensive application and execution.

The present findings confirm that while government officials may display policy comprehension, disparity can exist between and among branches. This affirms the need to of role definitions and targeted capacity-building, guaranteeing that PPPs at the local level are executed responsibly and effectively.

Section 2.2. Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Years of Service

This section reveals the comparison of the respondents' level of understanding regarding the IRR of the PPP Code with the quantity of years of service. With the analysis of the data provided, the researchers anticipated whether longer years in service leads to a better comprehension of PPP legal framework.

Table 6

Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Years of Service

Mean Rating	Position	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	P-Value	Decision
Level of Understanding	1.5 years and below	2.81	.50	Agree	10.393	.006**	Reject Ho
	2.6 to 15 years	3.09	.62	Agree			
	3.16 years and above	.62	.62	Agree			
Overall		2.98	.57	Agree			

Significant Level at <0.05.

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Strong Disagree; 1.50 – 2.49: Disagree; 2.50 – 3.49: Agree; 3.50 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 6 shows that the p-value generated was 0.461 indicating that the years of service does not affect the concerned officials' level of understanding of the PPP in terms of its legal framework. The answers of the respondents resulted in "Agree" ($\bar{x}=2.98$, $SD=0.57$). Particularly, for the years 16 and above service rendered has the highest rating of ($\bar{x}=3.10$, $SD=0.62$). In contrast, the years 5 and below indicate the lowest which is ($\bar{x}=2.81$, $SD=0.50$). Familiarity with PPPs is not a function of tenure, but is rather a direct experience with PPP projects and commitment to continuous learning.

Early institution of PPP frameworks is not tantamount to immediate and equal familiarity and capacity across all levels and departments of the government. Therefore, while years of service may bring general management skills, a lack of understanding regarding the unique complexities of joint ventures such as risk allocation, contractual nuances, and stakeholder management can lead to flawed decision-making, inefficient processes, and ultimately, project underperformance. Consequently, occurring tendencies of having a detrimental impact on experienced personnel operating without adequate PPP-specific knowledge, reliance on outdated knowledge can hinder the adoption of contemporary best practices and innovative PPP models, limiting the potential for achieving greater value for money and project success (ADB, 2018). Moreover, the highly complex and technical nature of PPP necessitates specialized knowledge and regular capacity development exposures, which are not automatically obtained through tenure alone.

According to Akinbo et al. (2023), the dimensions of knowledge management barriers are based on the features of PPP and lacking knowledge management competencies. Overcoming these barriers means introducing improvement strategies such as training and development of PPP stakeholders on knowledge management tools, legislative backing on using knowledge tools for storing PPP projects, and participation from relevant parties in information sharing needs to be implemented.

Therefore, true understanding stems from active participation in the different phases of PPP projects, coupled with dedicated efforts in training, knowledge acquisition, and staying abreast of evolving legal and policy landscapes. Without this specific exposure and ongoing education, even highly tenured personnel may possess a superficial grasp, potentially leading to critical errors in the negotiation, implementation, and oversight of PPP initiatives.

Section 2.3. Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on the IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Seminars Attended in the Last 12 Months

In this section, the researchers compared the respondents' level of understanding regarding the IRR of the PPP code with the quantity of seminars they participated in the last 12 months. The researchers anticipate to identify whether attending more seminars leads to a better understanding of PPP guidelines and operations.

Table 7

Comparison in the Level of Understanding of Respondents on IRR of the PPP Code in terms of Seminars Attended in the Last 12 Months

Mean Rating	Position	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Mann-Whitney U	P-Value	Decision
Level of Understanding	No seminars attended	2.82	.56	Agree	48.500	.006**	Reject Ho
	Attended Seminars	3.38	.40	Agree			
Overall		2.98	.57	Agree			

Significant Level at <0.05.

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Strong Disagree; 1.50 – 2.49: Disagree; 2.50 – 3.49: Agree; 3.50 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 7 shows a statistically significant disparity in the selected Solano LGU officials' understanding of the IRR of the PPP Code. The null hypothesis is rejected because the calculated p-value is 0.006, which is less than the acceptable threshold of 0.05. In particular, seminar participants ($\bar{x}=3.38$, $SD=0.40$) showed a greater degree of comprehension than non-participants ($\bar{x}=2.82$, $SD=0.56$). The total mean of 2.98, which is within the "Agree" range, indicates that although the majority of respondents had an overall knowledge of the IRR of the PPP Code, attending seminars greatly improved their comprehension.

The gap between these means that attending seminars is essential for improving understanding of PPP policies and implementation processes. This analysis underlines the necessity of continual knowledge and ability improvement for LGU officials, notably through established seminars and training sessions centered on PPP frameworks. Engaging in such ventures could contribute to better knowledgeable choices and greater success in partnerships pursuant to the PPP Code. This suggests that attending seminars about PPP has a beneficial impact on the respondents' understanding.

The findings of this section is parallel to Public-Private Partnership Center (2025), wherein it was stated that by developing their comprehension of the principles of PPPs, the Philippine PPP Program, and the crucial factors in establishing PPP institutions, attending training and seminars seeks to equip participating agencies to carry out PPPs. More so, Liu et al. (2023) argued that there is still a pressing need for additional training on PPP development, especially for the procurement of the public sector organizations, even though certain advanced economies have set up national or local offices for generating lessons learned and offering advice on implementing public-private partnerships.

For LGU officials, attending PPP seminars is essential because it improves their comprehension of how to work effectively with the private sector, gives them efficient instruments

for executing projects, and guarantees service delivery. Through organized, accessible, and profitable collaborations, these seminars enable officials to promote local economic growth.

Section 3. Extent of the Capability of the Respondents on the Implementation of PPP in terms of the PPP Process

The data collected about the respondents' capacity in carrying out PPP projects, particularly with regard to the PPP process, is analyzed in this section. The primary elements namely development, approval, competition, and cooperation are highlighted in the analysis, which also determine the findings according to the knowledge and perspectives of the respondents. The study anticipates the advantages and disadvantages of present capability extents along with the groundwork for future advancements in PPP implementation.

Table 8

Extent of Capability of the Respondents on the Implementation of Public-Private Partnership in terms of the PPP Process

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. The LGU is aware of PPP projects' legal, financial, and fundamental technical issues.	3.44	.66	Agree
2. The LGU employs sufficient technical capacity to ensure construction and service standards.	3.41	.74	Agree
3. The LGU has determined local development goals in accordance with the implementation of PPP.	3.47	.74	Agree
4. The LGU has internal expertise in accounting, financial management, and commercial legal issues.	3.44	.74	Agree
5. The LGU has strategic planning sessions and preparations to ensure the effective implementation of PPP in the future.	3.29	.79	Agree
6. The LGU explicitly includes PPPs in the development plan or strategy as an infrastructure delivery and service provision mechanism.	3.44	.74	Agree
7. The LGU conducts feasibility studies to test the viability of the proposed PPP projects.	3.29	.75	Agree
8. The LGU identifies the need for internal assessment and feasibility consultations regarding PPP implementation in the municipality.	3.50	.70	Strongly Agree
9. The LGU has legal support for implementing and negotiating future PPP agreements.	3.44	.74	Agree
10. The LGU plans to engage with the local community in the planning and decision-making for implementing PPP in the municipality.	3.55	.66	Strongly Agree
11. The LGU experienced negotiating with a proponent of terms of the PPP undertaking once an unsolicited proposal was evaluated positively.	3.14	.82	Agree
12. The LGU has an existing Prequalification, Bids, and Awards Committee (PBAC).	3.70	.67	Strongly Agree
13. The LGU's bid terms, conditions, and evaluation criteria are clear and consistently applied.	3.58	.65	Strongly Agree
14. The LGU has plans for capacity-building to support PPP implementation in the municipality.	3.52	.70	Strongly Agree
15. The LGU's potential bidders are given equal opportunities and access and are bound by the same timeline.	3.41	.70	Agree
16. The LGU has a designated team with commercial and financial skills who would be available to oversee the PPP project.	3.11	.84	Agree
17. The LGU has experience in preparing financial cash flow.	3.55	.70	Strongly Agree
18. The LGU oversees, audits, and discloses procedures and institutions in place.	3.38	.77	Agree
19. The LGU's project liabilities are monitored under its accounting.	3.58	.70	Strongly Agree
20. The LGU and private sector support and commit to implementing the project.	3.52	.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.44	.59	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Strongly Disagree; 1.50 – 2.49: Disagree; 2.50 – 3.49: Agree; 3.50 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

A. Development Stage

Table 8 indicates that in the development stage of the PPP process, where the statement of “The LGU plans to engage with the local community in the planning and decision-making for implementing PPP in the municipality,” has the highest mean value in terms of this part of Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) process where $\bar{x}=3.55$ and $SD=0.66$ that falls on the range on the scale of “Strongly Agree.” On the other hand, the statement of “The LGU conducts feasibility studies to test the viability of the proposed PPP projects,” has the lowest mean value regarding the development part of the PPP process where $\bar{x}=3.29$ and $SD=0.75$ falls in the range on the scale of “Agree.” In contrast, the need for internal assessment and feasibility consultations regarding PPP implementation in the municipality falls under the “Strongly Agree” range.

These results imply that the LGU is set to involve their community in PPP planning and decision-making which demonstrate a dedication to openness, diversity, and involvement in governance. This also means that effective and efficient local backing for PPP initiatives, more adaptable and sustainable projects, and an improvement in trust among citizens can all result from the use of this approach. It suggests that through carrying out feasibility studies, acknowledging the necessity of in-depth evaluations and discussions, coordinating initiatives with local advancement objectives, and staying informed about legal, financial, and technical factors, the LGU appears to be taking an anticipatory and effective approach to PPP implementation, according to the research findings.

Liu et al. (2023) argued that economic conditions are a significant external element, internal considerations that help determine the suitability of PPP initiatives include the feasibility of the project, return on monetary resources, and satisfaction with the project. As a result, a number of studies concentrate on how PPP ventures react to the economic climate. Existing influences on risk assessment, economic viability assessment, and value for money assessment have an immediate effect on PPP effectiveness.

Moreover, the study of Alghamdi et al. (2022) shows that several crucial socioeconomic concession factors are involved in PPP and must be identified throughout the PPP process. However, because of the mutual dependence among these aspects, determining them poses challenges for decision-makers. The development of PPP agreements can be improved by evaluating the constantly changing and interconnected ties among the socioeconomic concession aspects.

The development stage of the PPP process is crucial since it establishes the framework for a project's effective execution. This stage helps draw in private sector investment, encourages openness, and integrates projects with national development goals by guaranteeing careful preparation, evaluation of risks, and stakeholder participation. In the end, this contributes to better public services and sustainably increasing infrastructure.

B. Approval Stage

In the approval stage, respondents' capacity falls in the range of “Agree” to “Strongly Agree.” Among the questions, the lowest mean generated was $\bar{x}= 3.44$, meanwhile, the highest recorded was $\bar{x}= 3.55$. These results suggest that the selected public officials generally perceive themselves to have a moderate to high level of capacity in handling the approval phase of PPP, manifesting the confidence of the officials in the internal system. However, scrutiny discloses several capacity gaps.

The primary risks associated with PPP projects encompass legal, regulatory, and financial concerns, as they substantially influence project duration and possess a reasonably high likelihood of occurrence, thus classified as high-risk factors (Ozorhon & Demirkesen Çakır, 2015). Nugroho et al. (2024) affirmed that the possibility of PPP errors in estimating demand, cost, and revenue predictions is a frequent occurrence. Consequently, financial risk reduction strategies are essential. Akomea-Frimpong et al. (2024) identified financial risk management strategies derived from feasibility studies on project financial viability, the application of sustainable financial risk assessment models, and the necessity for the engagement of community leaders and users in financial risk management plans.

In view of the findings, a strategic combat to substantiate financial and legal expertise, impart sustainable risk management approaches, and concretize the LGU officials' capacity to moderate high-risk potentials in the development and every phase of PPP, is crucial.

C. Competition Stage

The data of the competition phase shows that the respondents capacity leans towards agreeing to agree strongly. The competition phase indicates that Statement 12 has the highest mean value of 3.70, pertaining to strongly agreeing *that the LGU has an existing Prequalification, Bids, and Awards Committee (PBAC)*, following the item above is Statement 13 bearing the value of 3.58, still within the range of strongly agree and pertains that *the LGU's bid terms, conditions, and evaluation criteria are clear and consistently applied. Bearing the value of 3.41, Statement 15 falls within agreement that the LGU's potential bidders are given equal opportunities and access and are bound by the same timeline*, following the item above is Statement 11 with a value of 3.14 pertaining that *the LGU experienced negotiating with a proponent of terms of the PPP undertaking once an unsolicited proposal was evaluated positively*. Revealing a value of 3.11, Statement 16 still falls within the agreement that the LGU has a designated team with commercial and financial skills who would be available to oversee the PPP project.

These indicate that the concerned officials of the LGU officials perceive themselves to have a moderate to high level of capability in handling the competition phase. The diverse levels of answers ranging from the highest 3.70 to the lowest 3.11, shows that the elected officials of LGU Solano are likely aware of the process of the competition phase and the joint effort of the public and private sectors. The LGU officials are well aware of the existence of the committee overseeing the competitive selection process of private sector partners in its locality and show consistency on their criteria for applicants, but somehow do not strongly agree on equal opportunities and access, negotiated with a proponent and has a designated team with commercial and financial skills overseeing the overall joint venture project.

The delivery of the infrastructure project or service as outlined in the agreement, such as open tenders versus negotiated procedures, and the impact of bid evaluation methodologies on project outcomes (Grimsey et al., 2015). Ultimately, for LGUs, a rigorous competition phase is not just a good practice but a vital mechanism for effective resource utilization, good governance, and successful local development.

D. Cooperation Stage

Table 8 reveals an overall mean score of 3.44 with an SD of 0.59, indicating that respondents generally agree to have the capability to implement PPP, with a tendency toward strong agreement in some indicators. Regarding the Cooperation Stage, the highest mean score 3.58, which is found in

Statement 19, *'The LGU's project liabilities are monitored under its accounting.'* This suggests that the LGU are highly attentive to monitoring project liabilities through their accounting systems. Similarly, Statement 20 ($\bar{x}=3.52$), *'The LGU and private sector support and commit to implementing the project'* reflects strong collaboration and commitment between the public sector and the private sector, underscoring the importance of mutual support in PPP projects. Other indicators such as *'The LGU has strategic planning sessions and preparations to ensure the effective implementation of PPP in the future, The LGU explicitly includes PPPs in the development plan or strategy as an infrastructure delivery and service provision mechanism, and The LGU oversees, audits, and discloses procedures and institutions in place,'* also scored above 3.29 mean score, showing a generally foreseeing stance from the local officials.

These findings imply that the LGU officials are aware of and actively engaging in practices that strengthen the cooperative stage in the PPP implementation. The high fiscal monitoring and institutional coordination scores suggest a growing maturity in LGU officials' capacity to manage complex, multi-actor projects. However, since the scores fall shortly below the *"Strongly Agree"* range, there is a room for further enhancement in strategic alignment, transparency mechanisms, and long-term commitment-building. This also reflects a positive trend in how the LGU officials move beyond passive policy compliance to more strategic and accountable public-private engagements.

The results align with findings from Navarro (2024), who identifies that many LGUs have begun to move beyond compliance-based approaches toward more proactive engagement. The relatively high scores indicate that the LGU is growing in financial maturity. Fiscal monitoring is a technical skill and a governance accountability, reflecting a shift toward institutional responsibility and risk awareness. Haydarov and Soriano (2016) argue that PPP success relies heavily on local capacity-building, especially in strategy, legal knowledge, and coordination. The data validates this, showing that LGUs increasingly integrate PPPs in development planning and strategic sessions. While these scores are promising, they also reveal an area that still requires enhancement, particularly if LGUs shift to long-term institutionalized planning.

Conclusion

The LGU Solano officials are ready to carry out upcoming PPP projects, demonstrating knowledge with the PPP Code's internal rate of return and a fundamental comprehension of its local applicability. Focused training, skills development, and the incorporation of sound PPP processes into future governance are necessitated by the challenges posed by deficiencies in technical competence, administrative knowledge, and domain-specific expertise, particularly in the administrative and economic sectors.

Equal bidder competition and disclosure concerns persist even though officials show proficiency in the PPP process of development and exhibit a proactive attitude by engaging the community. Their changing governance style shows that they are prepared to handle challenging initiatives, but it still calls for more effective execution and management. Overall, PPP provide benefits in breakthroughs, job creation, and provision of services, but also poses problems in governance, financing, and acceptance among society; therefore, successful implementation depends on efficient and transparent administration.

Recommendations

A complete strategy is suggested to successfully implement PPP in Solano, starting with a policy orientation session for municipal officials on the IRR of the PPP Code. This seminar ought to

be inclusive, covering particular issues and designated tasks. The PPP Center may help with this by creating a consolidated understanding of case studies and guidelines and by offering training that is specific to the economic and political setting of each community.

In order to improve officials' abilities to start and oversee PPP initiatives, LGU Solano may also hold technical training sessions for capacity building in partnership with the PPP Center. The PPP Center may also set up a tracking and assessment structure with frequent audits and public accounting records to guarantee reliability and openness. Transparency in selecting collaborators and making decisions requires bolstering administrative coherence, fostering stakeholder participation, and enlisting the public. Lastly, it is advised that additional studies be done to examine power disparities, execution gaps, and the comparability between PPP and privatization.

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